

The H -Line Signed Graph of a Signed Graph

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Abstract: A *Smarandachely k -signed graph* (*Smarandachely k -marked graph*) is an ordered pair $S = (G, \sigma)$ ($S = (G, \mu)$) where $G = (V, E)$ is a graph called *underlying graph of S* and $\sigma : E \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$ ($\mu : V \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$) is a function, where each $\bar{e}_i \in \{+, -\}$. Particularly, a Smarandachely 2-signed graph or Smarandachely 2-marked graph is called abbreviated a *signed graph* or a *marked graph*. Given a connected graph H of order at least 3, the *H -Line Graph* of a graph $G = (V, E)$, denoted by $HL(G)$, is a graph with the vertex set E , the edge set of G where two vertices in $HL(G)$ are adjacent if, and only if, the corresponding edges are adjacent in G and there exists a copy of H in G containing them. Analogously, for a connected graph H of order at least 3, we define the *H -Line signed graph* $HL(S)$ of a signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$ as a signed graph, $HL(S) = (HL(G), \sigma')$, and for any edge e_1e_2 in $HL(S)$, $\sigma'(e_1e_2) = \sigma(e_1)\sigma(e_2)$. In this paper, we characterize signed graphs S which are H -line signed graphs and study some properties of H -line graphs as well as H -line signed graphs.

Key Words: Smarandachely k -Signed graphs, Smarandachely k -Marked graphs, Signed graphs, Balance, Switching, H -Line signed graph.

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§1. Introduction

For standard terminology and notion in graph theory we refer the reader to Harary [8]; the non-standard will be given in this paper as and when required. We treat only finite simple graphs without self loops and isolates.

A *Smarandachely k -signed graph* (*Smarandachely k -marked graph*) is an ordered pair $S = (G, \sigma)$ ($S = (G, \mu)$) where $G = (V, E)$ is a graph called *underlying graph of S* and $\sigma : E \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$ ($\mu : V \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$) is a function, where each $\bar{e}_i \in \{+, -\}$. Particularly, a Smarandachely 2-signed graph or Smarandachely 2-marked graph is called abbreviated a *signed*

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graph or a *marked graph*. We say that a signed graph is *connected* if its underlying graph is connected. A signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$ is *balanced* if every cycle in S has an even number of negative edges (See [9]). Equivalently a signed graph is balanced if product of signs of the edges on every cycle of S is positive.

A *marking* of S is a function $\mu : V(G) \rightarrow \{+, -\}$; A signed graph S together with a marking μ is denoted by S_μ .

The following characterization of balanced signed graphs is well known.

Theorem 1.1(E. Sampathkumar [12]) *A signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$ is balanced if, and only if, there exists a marking μ of its vertices such that each edge uv in S satisfies $\sigma(uv) = \mu(u)\mu(v)$.*

Given a signed graph S one can easily define a marking μ of S as follows: For any vertex $v \in V(S)$,

$$\mu(v) = \prod_{uv \in E(S)} \sigma(uv),$$

the marking μ of S is called *canonical marking* of S .

The idea of switching a signed graph was introduced by Abelson and Rosenberg [1] in connection with structural analysis of marking μ of a signed graph S . Switching S with respect to a marking μ is the operation of changing the sign of every edge of S to its opposite whenever its end vertices are of opposite signs. The signed graph obtained in this way is denoted by $S_\mu(S)$ and is called *μ -switched signed graph* or just *switched signed graph*. Two signed graphs $S_1 = (G, \sigma)$ and $S_2 = (G', \sigma')$ are said to be *isomorphic*, written as $S_1 \cong S_2$ if there exists a graph isomorphism $f : G \rightarrow G'$ (that is a bijection $f : V(G) \rightarrow V(G')$ such that if uv is an edge in G then $f(u)f(v)$ is an edge in G') such that for any edge $e \in G$, $\sigma(e) = \sigma'(f(e))$. Further a signed graph $S_1 = (G, \sigma)$ *switches* to a signed graph $S_2 = (G', \sigma')$ (or that S_1 and S_2 are *switching equivalent*) written $S_1 \sim S_2$, whenever there exists a marking μ of S_1 such that $S_\mu(S_1) \cong S_2$. Note that $S_1 \sim S_2$ implies that $G \cong G'$, since the definition of switching does not involve change of adjacencies in the underlying graphs of the respective signed graphs.

Two signed graphs $S_1 = (G, \sigma)$ and $S_2 = (G', \sigma')$ are said to be *weakly isomorphic* (see [22]) or *cycle isomorphic* (see [23]) if there exists an isomorphism $\phi : G \rightarrow G'$ such that the sign of every cycle Z in S_1 equals to the sign of $\phi(Z)$ in S_2 . The following result is well known (See [23]):

Theorem 1.2(T. Zaslavsky [23]) *Two signed graphs S_1 and S_2 with the same underlying graph are switching equivalent if, and only if, they are cycle isomorphic.*

§2. H-Line Signed Graph of a Signed Graph

The line graph $L(G)$ of a nonempty graph $G = (V, E)$ is the graph whose vertices are the edges of G and two vertices are adjacent if and only if the corresponding edges are adjacent. The triangular line graph $\mathcal{T}(G)$ of a nonempty graph was introduced by Jerret [10] as a graph whose vertices are edges of G and two vertices are adjacent if and only if corresponding edges belongs to a common triangle. Triangular graphs were introduced to model a metric space defined on

the edge set of a graph. These concepts were generalized in [5] as follows: Let H be a fixed connected graph of order at least 3. For a graph G of size the H -line graph of G , denoted by $HL(G)$, is the graph whose vertices are the edges of G and two vertices are adjacent the corresponding edges are adjacent and belong to a copy of H . If $H \cong P_3$ then $HL(G) = L(G)$ and so H -line graph is a generalization of line graphs. Clearly, if a graph is H free, then its H -line graph is trivial.

In [10], the authors introduced the notion of triangular line graph of a graph as follows: The *triangular line graph* of a $G = (V, E)$ denoted by $\mathcal{T}(G) = (V', E')$, whose vertices are the edges of G and two vertices are adjacent the corresponding edges belongs to a triangle in G . Clearly for any graph G , $\mathcal{T}(G) = K_3L(G)$.

Behzad and Chartrand [3] introduced the notion of *line signed graph* $L(S)$ of a given signed graph S as follows: $L(S)$ is a signed graph such that $(L(S))^u \cong L(S^u)$ and an edge $e_i e_j$ in $L(S)$ is negative if, and only if, both e_i and e_j are adjacent negative edges in S . Another notion of line signed graph introduced in [7], is as follows: The *line signed graph* of a signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$ is a signed graph $L(S) = (L(G), \sigma')$, where for any edge ee' in $L(S)$, $\sigma'(ee') = \sigma(e)\sigma(e')$. In this paper, we follow the notion of line signed graph defined by M. K. Gill [7] (See also E. Sampathkumar et al. [13,14]). For more operations on signed graphs see [15-20].

Proposition 2.1 *For any signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$, its line signed graph $L(S) = (L(G), \sigma')$ is balanced.*

In [21], the authors extends the notion of triangular line graphs to triangular line signed graphs. We now extend the notion of H -line graph to the realm of signed graph as follows:

Let $S = (G, \sigma)$ be a signed graph. For any fixed connected graph H of order at least 3, the H -line signed graph of S , denoted by $HL(S)$ is the signed graph $HL(S) = (HL(G), \sigma')$ whose underlying graph is $HL(G)$ and for any edge ee' in $HL(G)$, $\sigma'(ee') = \sigma(e)\sigma(e')$. Further a signed graph S is said to be H -line signed graph if there exists a signed graph S' such that $HL(S') \cong S$.

We now give a straightforward, yet interesting property of H -line signed graphs.

Theorem 2.2 *For any connected graph H of order at least 3 and for any signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$, its H -line signed graph $HL(S)$ is balanced.*

Proof Let σ' denote the signing of $HL(S)$ and let the signing σ of S be treated as a marking of the vertices of $HL(S)$. Then by definition of $HL(S)$ we see that $\sigma'(e_1, e_2) = \sigma(e_1)\sigma(e_2)$, for every edge (e_1, e_2) of $HL(S)$ and hence, by Theorem 1.1, the result follows. \square

Corollary 2.3 *For any two signed graphs S_1 and S_2 with the same underlying graph, $HL(S_1) \sim HL(S_2)$.*

The following result characterizes signed graphs which are H -line signed graphs.

Theorem 2.4 *A signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$ is a H -line signed graph for some connected graph H of order at least 3 if, and only if, S is balanced signed graph and its underlying graph G is a*

H-line graph.

Proof Suppose that S is H -line signed graph. Then there exists a signed graph $S' = (G', \sigma')$ such that $HL(S') \cong S$. Hence by definition $HL(G) \cong G'$ and by Theorem 2.2, S is balanced.

Conversely, suppose that $S = (G, \sigma)$ is balanced and G is H -line graph. That is there exists a graph G' such that $HL(G') \cong G$. Since S is balanced by Theorem 1.1, there exists a marking μ of vertices of S such that for any edge $uv \in G$, $\sigma(uv) = \mu(u)\mu(v)$. Also since $G \cong HL(G')$, vertices in G are in one-to-one correspondence with the edges of G' . Now consider the signed graph $S' = (G', \sigma')$, where for any edge e' in G' to be the marking on the corresponding vertex in G . Then clearly $HL(S') \cong S$ and so S is H -line graph. \square

For any positive integer k , the k^{th} iterated H -line signed graph, $HL^k(S)$ of S is defined as follows:

$$HL^0(S) = S, \quad HL^k(S) = HL(HL^{k-1}(S)).$$

Corollary 2.5 *Given a signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$ and any positive integer k , $HL^k(S)$ is balanced, for any connected graph H of order ≥ 3 .*

In [6], the authors proved the following for a graph G its H -line graph $HL(G)$ is isomorphic to G then H is a path or a cycle. Analogously we have the following.

Theorem 2.6 *If a signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$ satisfies $S \sim HL(S)$ then S is balanced and H is a cycle or a path.*

Theorem 2.7 *For any cycle C_k on $k \geq 3$ vertices, a connected graph G on $n \geq r$ vertices satisfies $C_k L(G) \cong G$ if, and only if, $G = C_k$.*

Proof Suppose that $C_k L(G) \cong G$. Then clearly, G must be unicyclic. Since $C_k L(G) \cong G$, we observe that G must contain a cycle C_k . Next, suppose that G contains a vertex of degree ≥ 3 , then the vertex corresponding to the edge not on the cycle in $C_k L(G)$ will be isolated vertex. Hence G must be a cycle C_k .

Conversely, if $G = C_k$, then clearly for any two adjacent edges in C_k belongs to a copy of C_k and so $C_k L(G) \cong L(G)$. Since the line graph of any C_k is C_k itself, we have $C_k L(G) \cong G$. \square

Corollary 2.8 *For any cycle C_k on $k \geq 3$ vertices, a graph G on $n \geq r$ vertices satisfies $C_k L(G) \cong G$ if, and only if, G is 2-regular and every component of G is C_k .*

In view of the above theorem we have,

Theorem 2.9 *For any cycle C_k on $k \geq 3$ vertices, a signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$ connected graph G on $n \geq r$ vertices satisfies $C_k L(S) \sim S$ if, and only if, $G = C_k$.*

Theorem 2.10 *For a path P_k on $k \geq 3$ vertices a connected graph G on $n \geq r$ vertices which contains a cycle of length $r > k$ satisfies $P_k L(G) \cong L(G)$ if, and only if, $G = C_n$ and $n \geq k$.*

Proof The result follows if $k = 3$, since $P_3 L(G) = L(G)$. Assume that $k \geq 4$. Clearly G must contain at least k vertices. Suppose that $P_k L(G) \cong L(G)$ and G contains a cycle of

length $r \geq k$. Then number of vertices in G and number of edges are equal. Hence G must be unicyclic. Since G contains a cycle of length $r > k$, then any two adjacent edges in C of G belongs to a common P_k . Hence $P_k L(G)$ also contains a cycle of length r . Next, suppose that G contains a vertex of degree ≥ 3 , then the vertex corresponding to the edge not on the cycle in $P_k L(G)$ will be adjacent to two adjacent vertices forming a C_3 and so $HL(G)$ is not unicyclic. Hence G must be the cycle C_n .

Conversely, if $G = C_n$ and $n \geq k$, then clearly any two adjacent edges in C_k belongs to a copy of C_k and so $P_k L(G) \cong L(G)$. Since the line graph of C_n is C_n itself, $P_k L(G) \cong L(G)$. \square

Corollary 2.11 *For any path P_k on $k \geq 3$ vertices, a graph G on $n \geq r$ vertices satisfies $P_k L(G) \cong G$ if, and only if, G is 2-regular and every component of G is C_r , for some $r \geq k$.*

Analogously, we have the following for signed graphs:

Corollary 2.12 *For any path P_k on $k \geq 3$ vertices, a signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$ on $n \geq r$ vertices satisfies $P_k L(S) \sim S$ if, and only if, S is balanced and every component of G is C_r , for some $r \geq k$.*

In [10], the authors prove that for any graph G , $T(G) \cong L(G)$ if, and only if, $G = K_n$. Analogously, we have the following:

Theorem 2.13 *A graph G of order n satisfies $K_r L(G) \cong L(G)$ for some $r \leq n$ if, and only if, $G = K_n$.*

Proof The result is trivial if $k = n$. Suppose that $K_r L(G) \cong L(G)$ and G is not complete for some $r \leq n - 1$. Then there exists at least two nonadjacent vertices u and v in G . Now for any vertex w , the edges uw and vw are adjacent and hence the corresponding vertices are adjacent. But the edges uw and vw can not be adjacent in $K_r L(G)$ since any set of r vertices containing u and v can not induce complete subgraph K_r . Whence, the condition is necessary.

For sufficiency, suppose $G = K_n$ for some $n \geq r$. Then for any two adjacent vertices in $L(G)$, the corresponding edges adjacent edges in G belongs to some K_r . Hence they are also adjacent in $K_r L(G)$ and any two nonadjacent vertices in $L(G)$ remain nonadjacent. This completes the proof. \square

Analogously, we have the following result for signed graphs:

Theorem 2.14 *A signed graph $S = (G, \sigma)$ satisfies $K_r L(S) \sim L(S)$, for some $3 \leq k \leq |V(G)|$ if, and only if, S is a balanced on a complete graph.*

§3. Triangular Line Signed Graphs and (0, 1, -1) Matrices

Matrices are very good models to represent a graph. In general given a matrix $A = (a_{ij})$ of order $m \times n$ one can associate many graphs with it (see [11]). On the other hand given any graph G we can associate many matrices such adjacency matrix, incidence matrix etc (see [8]). Analogously, given a matrix with entries one can associate many signed graphs (See [11]). In

this section, we give a relation between the notion of triangular line graph and some graph associated with $\{0, 1\}$ -matrices. Also we extend this to triangular signed graphs and some signed graphs associated with matrices whose entries are $-1, 0$, or 1 .

Given a $(0, 1)$ -matrix A , the term graph $T(A)$ of A was defined as follows (See [2]): The vertex set of $T(A)$ consists of m row labels r_1, r_2, \dots, r_m and n column labels c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n of A and the edge set consists of the unordered pairs $r_i c_j$ for which $a_{ij} \neq 0$.

Given a $(0, 1)$ -matrix A of order $m \times n$, the graph $G_t(A)$ can be constructed as follows: The vertex set of $G_t(A)$ consists of non-zero entries of A and the edge set consists of distinct pairs of vertices (a_{ij}, a_{kr}) that lie in the same row ($i=k$) with $a_{ir} \neq 0$ or or same column($j=r$) with $a_{kj} \neq 0$. The following result relates the connects the two notions the term graph and G_t graph of a given matrix A :

Theorem 3.1 For any $(0, 1)$ -matrix A , $G_t(A) = T(T(A))$.

Let $A = (a_{ij})$ be any $m \times n$ matrix in which each entry belongs to the set $\{-1, 0, 1\}$; we shall call such a matrix a $(0, \pm 1)$ -matrix. The notion of term graph of a $(0, 1)$ -matrix can be easily extended to term signed graph of a $(0, \pm 1)$ -matrix A as follows (see [2]): The vertex set of $T(A)$ consists of m row labels r_1, r_2, \dots, r_m and n column labels c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n of A , the edge set consists of the unordered pairs $r_i c_j$ for which $a_{ij} \neq 0$ and the sign of the edge $r_i c_j$ is the sign of the nonzero entry a_{ij} .

Next, given any $(0, \pm 1)$ -matrix A a *triangular matrix signed graph* $Sg_t(A)$ of A can be constructed as follows: The vertex set of $Sg_t(A)$ is consists of nonzero entries of A and edge set consists of distinct pairs of vertices (a_{ij}, a_{kr}) that lie in the same row ($i = k$) with $a_{ir} \neq 0$ or same column ($j = r$) with $a_{kj} \neq 0$; the sign of an edge uv in $Sg(A)$ is defined as the product of sings of the entries of A that correspond to $u = a_{ij}$ and $v = a_{kr}$.

The following is a observation whose proof follows from the definition of triangular line graph and the facts just mentioned above:

Theorem 3.2 For any $(0, \pm 1)$ matrix A , $Sg_t(A) \cong T(T_g(A))$.

The *Kronecker product* or *tensor product* of two signed graphs S_1 and S_2 , denoted by $S_1 \otimes S_2$ is defined (see [2]) as follows:The vertex set of $(S_1 \otimes S_2)$ is $V(S_1) \times V(S_2)$, the edge set is $E(S_1 \otimes S_2) := \{(u_1, v_1), (u_2, v_2) : u_1 u_2 \in E(S_1), v_1 v_2 \in E(S_2)\}$ and the sign of the edge $(u_1, v_1)(u_2, v_2)$ is the product of the sign of $u_1 u_2$ in S_1 and the sign of $v_1 v_2$ in S_2 . In the following result, $A(S)$ will denote the usual adjacency matrix of the given signed graph S and $A \otimes B$ denotes the standard tensor product of the given matrices A and B .

Theorem 3.3(M. Acharya [2]) For any two signed graphs S_1 and S_2 , $A(S_1 \otimes S_2) = A(S_1) \otimes A(S_2)$.

Theorem 3.4 For any signed graph S , $T(A(S)) = S \otimes K_2^+$, where K_2^+ denotes the complete graph K_2 with its only edge treated as being positive.

The *adjacency signed graph* $\bar{\delta}(S)$ of a given signed graph S is the matrix signed graph $Sg(A(S))$ of the adjacency matrix $A(S)$ of S [2].

Theorem 3.5(M. Acharya [2]) For any signed graph S , $\bar{\delta}(S) = L(S \otimes K_2^+)$.

Analogously we define *triangular adjacency signed graph* of $A(S)$, the adjacency matrix of S denoted by $\bar{\delta}_t(S)$ as the signed graph $Sg_t(A(S))$. We have the following result.

Theorem 3.6 For any signed graph S , $\bar{\delta}_t(S) = \mathcal{T}(S \otimes K_2^+)$.

- [1] R. P. Abelson and M. J. Rosenberg, Symbolic psychologic: A model of attitudinal cognition, *Behav. Sci.*, 3 (1958), 1-13.
- [2] M. Acharya, x -Line sigraph of a sigraph, *J. Combin. Math. Combin. Comput.*, 69(2009), 103-111.
- [3] M. Behzad and G. T. Chartrand, Line-coloring of signed graphs, *Elemente der Mathematik*, 24(3) (1969), 49-52.
- [4] G. Chartrand, M. A Henning, E. B. Jarrett and C.E. Wall, Quadrilateral Line signed graphs-Preprint.
- [5] G. Chartrand, H. Gavlas and M. Schultz, H -distance in graphs, *Congress. Numer*, 101(1994), 3-15.
- [6] G. Chartrand, H. Gavlas and M. Schultz, Convergent sequence of iterated H -line graphs, *Discrete Mathematics*, 147(1995), 73-86.
- [7] M. K. Gill, *Contributions to some topics in graph theory and its applications*, Ph.D. Thesis, The Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, 1983.
- [8] F. Harary, *Graph Theory*, Addison-Wesley Publishing Co., 1969.
- [9] F. Harary, On the notion of balance of a signed graph, *Michigan Math. J.*, 2(1953), 143-146.
- [10] E. B. Jarrett, *Transformations of graphs and digraphs*, Ph.D. Thesis, Western Michigan University, 1991.
- [11] V. Mishra, *Graphs associated with $[0, 1]$ and $[0, +1, -1]$ matrices*, Ph.D. Thesis, The Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, 1975.
- [12] E. Sampathkumar, Point signed and line signed graphs, *Nat. Acad. Sci. Letters*, 7(3) (1984), 91-93.
- [13] E. Sampathkumar, P. Siva Kota Reddy, and M. S. Subramanya, The Line n -sigraph of a symmetric n -sigraph, *Southeast Asian Bull. Math.*, to appear.
- [14] E. Sampathkumar, M. S. Subramanya and P. Siva Kota Reddy, Characterization of Line Sidigraphs, *Southeast Asian Bull. Math.*(Springer-Verlag), to appear.
- [15] E. Sampathkumar, M. S. Subramanya and P. Siva Kota Reddy, Directionally n -signed graphs, *Proc. Int. Conf. ICDM 2008*, 13 (2010), 155162.
- [16] E. Sampathkumar, M. S. Subramanya and P. Siva Kota Reddy, Directionally n -signed graphs-II, *International J. Math. Combin.*, 4 (2009), 89-98.
- [17] P. Siva Kota Reddy and M. S. Subramanya, Signed graph equation $L^k(S) \sim \bar{S}$, *International J. Math. Combin.*, 4 (2009), 84-88.
- [18] P. Siva Kota Reddy, S. Vijay and H. C. Savithri, A Note on Path Sidigraphs, *International J. Math. Combin.*, 1 (2010), 42-46.

- [19] P. Siva Kota Reddy, S. Vijay and V. Lokesha, n^{th} Power signed graphs, *Proceedings of the Jangjeon Math. Soc.*, 12(3) (2009), 307-313.
- [20] P. Siva Kota Reddy, S. Vijay and V. Lokesha, n^{th} Power signed graphs-II, *International J. Math. Combin.*, 1 (2010), 74-79.
- [21] M. S. Subramanya and P. Siva Kota Reddy, Triangular line signed graph of a signed graph, *Advances and Applications in Discrete Mathematics*, 4(1) (2009), 17-23.
- [22] T. Sozánsky, Enumeration of weak isomorphism classes of signed graphs, *J. Graph Theory*, 4(2)(1980), 127-144.
- [23] T. Zaslavsky, Signed Graphs, *Discretas Appl. Math.*, 4(1)(1982), 47-74.